
Portrayal of Militants

A comparison of Daily Dawn and Daily New York Times Editorials(2001-2010)

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ABSTRACT

The research work named “Portrayal of militants, a comparison of Daily Dawn and Daily New York Times editorials (2001-2010)” is an attempt to find out the Pakistan and American press behavior towards militants. Militants are considered as the biggest threat for the world stability. In this research work, number of factors is there that how they gave birth and got developed by the passage of time. press is covered with the militants activities which are caused the death and destruction in all over the world .This research work is basically focus on this aspect that how Pakistan and America press portrayed militants in their top ranked newspapers. From Pakistan this is Daily Dawn and from America this is New York Times. The theoretical framework goes to the framing theory of Robert Entman which plainly states that the framing process is the process which selects some piece of reality and makes that realty more silent and real by discussing again and again. The findings depict that both Pakistan and American press portrayed militants as enemy and gave negative portrayal towards them.

INTRODUCTION

There is a vast history of terrorism and terrorist groups. From the ancient times people were used to the threat of fear for the attainment of their national, social, political and religious causes against administrative official or even innocent lives. The word “terrorism” was first used in the late 17th century in France (Schema 1989) when French people closed down the doors of monarch system forever in 1789. This is particularly known as French revolution. After the revolution France had seen the rivers of blood which was known as the great terror. Revolutionary government found themselves as the best at all sides. Modern terrorism can be seen from the late 19th and early 20th centuries. NORODNAYA & VOLYA were Russian terrorist groups whose aim was to finish Russian monarch system and the TSAR. The 2nd world war ended with the shifting of terrorism from Europe to the Middle East and Asia (Liqueur 2001). Now the 21st century is seeing the more Modern Terrorist groups having modern tactics. AL-Qaeda, Afghan Taliban, TTP are the few examples of the terrorist groups with different policies and agendas. In this research work we will find out the stance of American press and Pakistan press towards militants. Under militant umbrella there are three main militant groups including Al-Qaida, Tehrek-e-Taliban an Afghan Taliban.

TYPES of TERRORISM

Jerrold Post (2003) provided the list of typology of terrorism.

Criminal Terrorism means "The act of terrorism", which involves some illegal and illicit goals or operations. As far as Pathological Terrorism is concerned, it may be specified as an Act of terrorism due to mental illness. Another type of terrorism is Political Terrorism; Political objectives are involved in it that a terrorist group wants to secure. Political terrorism further is divided into 3 sub categories. Regime or State Terrorism means the Governments action to support and intimidate in using terror. Second type is State Support Terrorism and historically, number of states provided safe heavens to terrorist groups. This is the terrorism act asserted by the government. In sub State Terrorism there are nongovernmental groups and further divided in 5 categories. Social Revolutionary type is the group which desire to pack up the existing established order. Right-wing Terrorism is the organization, which wants to preserve a political system or to return society to some past or mythical time of greatness. Nationalist-separatist Terrorism is the group which wants to build a nation and achieve political autonomy and independence for their people. In Single-issue Terrorism, Groups, focus only on one issue, earth first! "The Earth Liberation Front". In Religious Extremist Terrorism, the main focus is on religion. This is further divided into two categories. In New Religion Terrorism, AUM SHINRIKYO, a Japanese group, is a best example of this type of terrorism. This group had strong belief that a sinful and impure is needed to kill and by doing this one will be liberate from all sins. In Fundamentalist Terrorism, different groups came in front after 9/11, having certain beliefs and ideas about the world and religion and try to convert whole system according to their will.

EXTREMISM in PAKISTAN

In the period of Hindu Muslim collaboration British India, Quaid-e-Azam was realized that both nations are different in their standards and could not survive with each other. Pakistan was not created in the name of Islam or Religion as Quaid-e-Azam himself cleared that religion is every individual's own matter. The main reason to get independence from Britain was political. In 1977, General Zia ul Haq overthrew the government of Zulfikar Ali Bhuto. Zia had close ties with extremists at that time for the survival of his government. In his period extremists got boost and they started looking reason for their strong existence in the region and projected that Pakistan was created in the name of Islam and spread the radical image of Islam around the world by his strategies and policies. His propaganda damaged the real ideology of getting independence from British rule. This was the start of extremism in Pakistan. In two decades, from 1977-89 and 1999-2008, General Zia and General Pervaiz Musharaf respectively had strong relations with militants and extremists. In the Zia regime these extremists were specially recruited and trained with latest techniques and weapons with the help of America. The term Jihad (holy war) got boost in that era, after Zia every government supported Jihadis (holy warriors) with sincerity and passion. This Jihadi infrastructure was specially developed against Soviet invasion in Afghanistan. They were supported by the US with latest infrastructure and military aid. These Jihadi fighters helped America a lot to achieve its objectives in Afghanistan. US backed anti Soviet Jihad in Afghanistan, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirate support to Taliban, realized Pakistan that Jihad is a common phenomenon and should help them out. After a U- turn policy of both America and Pakistan in the name of War on Terror, they fully neglected

those elements that at times were considered as the right arm for the country defense. Those all fighters were ignored by Pakistan and America both in psychological and economical concerns. After the rebirth of Al-Qaeda and beginning of local Taliban, they joined them and both Al-Qaeda and Afghan Taliban gained a lot from their skills and training for the attainment of their particular objectives. The seed of enmity was very strong sown among these fighters against Pakistan and America.

Jihadi groups and Jihadi culture were the outcome of Afghan jihad. One can say that the roots of militancy and extremism are found Afghan jihad which gave birth number of jihadi groups and jihadi culture after and before afghan jihad. Number of jihadi organizations in Pakistan, like:

1. Harkat-ul-Jihad-al-Islami (HJI) led by Qari Saifullah Akhter
2. Jamiat-ul-Ansar (JA) led by Mulana Khalil
3. Jaish-e-Muhamad (Jem) led by Mulana Masood Azher
4. Lashkar-e-Tayyaba (LeT)
5. Dawaul Irshad (MDI) led by Hafiz Muhammed Saeed
6. Hizb-ul-Mujahideen led by Yousaf Shauq.

These jihadi groups then turned into militant / terrorists and became great threat after joining Taliban, TTP and Al-Qaeda. The end of Afghan jihad was the start of terrorism and insurgency in Pakistan. The long afghan jihad made strong impacts on the Pakistani society and introduced a culture which was known as the “Kalashnikov Culture”

There are basically three phases of terrorism that led the society too much insecure and fear during this time

1. The first phase started in 1980 when an Indian sponsored terrorist organization conducted bomb blasts in different areas of Punjab. From 1998 to 2000 Pakistan suffered a number of terrorist attacks by the Indian terrorist groups. In 2002 President Pervaiz Musharf banned jihadi organizations by arresting the leaders of these organizations and this led to the problem for Pakistan’s internal security.
2. Second phase of terrorism started in Pakistan in 1980 when Sipah-e-Sahaba, Lashker-e-Jhangwi and Sipah-e- Muhammad started bomb blasts in entire Pakistan. They targeted official groups, administrative officers, bureaucrats, dignitaries of rival sects and even the innocent civilians. This phase continued till it was finished by arresting and killing their top leaders. These groups thus dispersed and joined Al-Qaeda, Taliban and TTP.
3. Third phase started in 2001 when after the US attack on Afghanistan the number of Al-Qaeda and Taliban activists fled towards the tribal areas of Pakistan like FATA and Waziristan, where they gained sympathy from local people and made a group named TTP which was not only a great threat for west but also for the Pakistanis sovereignty.

Ilahi discusses the additional four factors which are the foundation of maintaining the new militancy, local Taliban and jihadi infrastructure in Pakistan. These are Jihadi and sectarian parties were involved previously in the terrorist attacks in Pakistan and later involved in Fata and South Waziristan. Different jihadi organizations like HM, LeJ, JeM are the acquiescent by the nature as they can merge with any other organization to forward their militant activates. Fata is thought to be the safe heaven and hide out for the militants since 2001. Before 2001 it never came to the daylight as the safe areas for militants and terrorists. There is no administrative law in FATA just as in the other territories of Pakistan. There is Jirga, Malik, and the Frontier Crime Regulations (FCR). The Afghan war made this area ideal for the militants and gained a lot of

sympathy by the leaders of that area. Contaminate FATA provided a new option for the militants to uphold their position again. Madaris are considered to be world wide as the ideal place to grow for Taliban. The Afghan jihad reversed the image of Islamic teaching internationally. Research proved that the students who study in madrassah are more extreme in nature towards Kashmir jihad and towards militancy and Taliban as compared to the students who pass out from the other educational institute. Madrassah is the key point to brain wash youngsters towards the off beam teaching about jihad and Islam. ISI is considered another factor to boost the jihadi infrastructure in Pakistan. They are considered to have the close ties with Taliban and militancy. Owing to their support to these jihadi groups. Militancy is rising day by day. Ilahi (2010)

Background of Afghan Taliban

The history of Afghanistan is very uncertain. Previously it was the battle between Communism and Islam. In 1965 a pro USSR party was in rule which was taken over by the communist coup. In 1978 new government was found under the leadership of TARAQI, after that Amin and Karmal came into power. The situation was worst in Afghanistan. Afghan people wanted an Islamic state rather than the communist one. For this they nurtured Afghan mujahideen to counter Karmal forces. Karmal asked USSR for military help. In 1979 USSR troops entered in Afghanistan for the sake of communist ruler's help. America was also against communist and nourished them with technology. It was estimated that from 1982 to 1992 round about 35000 people were trained under the mujahideen cover. It was the period when Madrassah culture was developed. Number of madrassahs was funded by Zia and thousands of students around the globe sought admission there to learn the teachings of Islam. From here the culture of Jihad was got uprising. Osama bin Laden was one of them who were recruited by ISI. When Iraq invaded Kuwait, Osama opposed the Saudi King's offer to US troops to use their soil against Iraq. US troops remained in the Saudi Arabia even after the Kuwait liberation. Osama left for Sudan in 1992 but with the immense pressure from the Saudi King and the United States he had to depart Sudan as well and went to Afghanistan in 1996. From start he was under the Jalal Abad shura but when Taliban went over to Kabul he went under their shelter. As long as the USSR forces were in Afghanistan these mujahidin came to know as Holy Warrior but after withdrawal of USSR, in 1989 from Afghanistan, America stopped funding them and named those mujahidin and holy warrior as the terrorists. Osama and the Afghan Taliban were the creation of US but when the same Osama was involved in the 9/11 attack they invaded Afghanistan and seized the government from Taliban and established a democratic government under the leadership of Hamid Karzi. Islam (2005)

Background of Al-Qaida

In late 1980, Al-Qaida was founded by Osama bin Laden with Arabs who did make fight with Soviets in Afghanistan: they were responsible for the bombing in Africa (1998), Yemen (2000), US (2001), Spain (2004), Great Britain (2005) and India (2006). Al-Qaida is now dispersed in the world around like Pakistan, Iran and Indonesia. Mingst (2008) Osama bin Laden started Al-Qaida in Peshawar as the service center for the Arabs to promote Wahabism in Afghanistan; this system was strictly practiced in the Arab countries. Thackrah (2004) Al-Qaida is an ideological organization which started the war against America to get rid of the US hold on Islamic states. Al-Qaida had a strong network in all over the world and based on the ideology of

holy war against the America and the Fatwas (religious decree regarding civil and religion). These Fatwas were signed by the different terrorist groups. Rehman (2011) Bin laden publicly accepted the attacks on America. After that US led forces on Afghanistan.

Background of TTP

In 2002 some tribal groups started supporting Al-Qaeda and Taliban. On 14 December 2007 they formed Tehrk-e-Taliban. They didn't concern with madrassahs and their training but they used their name for boosting themselves. The key objectives of them are

1. The resistance against Pakistan Security Forces
2. Helped the Afghan Taliban
3. Imposition of Nizam-e-Shariah

Apart from these objectives they have some sort of domestic objectives as well. As they received heavy amount of money to keep busy Pakistan military forces from AT and Al-Qaeda. All the TTP members are not extremists; different people joined TTP for different reasons. For instance, for the sake of unemployment, criminals are in TTP with big ratio. TTP has very strong hold in 24 districts, seven tribal agencies and 6 frontier regions. Ilahi (2010)

Review of Al-Qaeda

Wade & Malijevic (2010) say that the western involvement with Arab countries to counter terrorism was the reason for Islamic militants to attack them and the main reason to create different Islamist militant groups to propagate against west and gain the sympathy of moderate Muslims. Al-Qaeda was the one of that groups founded by Usama Bin Laden in 1988. Their main objective is to remove American and western control over Muslim countries. They are like the Red Army faction in Germany who was active during 1960 and 1970. Pape (2005) says that Al-Qaeda has less fundamentalist goals rather than a simple strategic goal to compel the United States and its western allies to withdraw combat forces from the Muslim countries. Roy (2004) says that for Al-Qaeda, every conflict is only because of western policies towards Muslim Ummah. They have actual problem with the destructing policies that west impose on third world countries especially on Muslim countries in the name of economic and strengthening stability of world. Haback (2006) says that jihadist have ideology about jihad and Islam in their own perspectives. Al-Qaeda ideology is circled around the oneness of God, Struggle, Islamic state and a call to turn away from false gods and the worship of the one real GOD, ALLAH. They believed that they are only the believers and go to Jannat for their right deeds. Helmes (2005) says that Al-Qaeda have secular aim of War with us. They want to drive the US force out of the Gulf. They want to end up the US support for Egypt and the most important to end up US support for Israel. Rehman (2011) considers Al-Qaeda as the ideology not the enemy. He says that because of the strict actions of the west and America Al-Qaeda influence is on the increase in the region. The ideology of Al-Qaeda is the Holy War based on the Fatwas signed by Osama Bin Laden which means the war against west and Israel. The factors which are common among all the extremist groups for the use of religion or the attainment of political and social agendas. They want to make an ideal government based of sharia and they consider jihad as holly war for themselves. The main aim of jihad is to eliminate the miss deeds in the society and restores the reform, well being and prosperity and the most important to eliminate the factors which are the root cause of spreading true things. This ideology cannot be ended by the war and destructive

power. The war is increasing their influence day by day in the society especially afghan border is the main place where they are frequently increasing their power by the help and support of regional community. The attacks on madras's and the attacks on militants is the main fact making their hold more strong and the main cause for weakening war on terror. Cassidy (2006) says that groups affiliated with Al-Qaeda have their own structure, policy, command controls and communication structures. He says that the enemy of America is very keen, complex natured, adoptive, asymmetric, and dispersed, net worked and also have capability of re building and re generation structures. There are four in entities of Al-Qaeda that they reorganized in 1988. The main purpose of these entities is to spread the radical image of Islam. These entities are

1. Parametrical structure
2. Global network of terrorists
3. Guerilla warfare
4. Loose alliance of transnational insurgent and terrorist groups

These entities main cause is to spread radical Islam. They have the ideology of global Jihad having some historical roots. Likewise the colonial rule imposition over Muslims; West destructive policies towards Muslims and Military defeats by the west to Muslims. All these factors are the causes of revenge towards west and America. The Al-Qaeda uses the suffered Muslims around the globe and uses them for their Guerrilla warfare in the Afghanistan and around the world. Chechnya, Bosnia, Labnan, Palestine, Iraq are the countries where they have maximum hold and used the people against the western countries and Israel. Casidy focuses on the four ideologies positions that exist in the Muslim world.

1. Secularist
2. Traditionalist
3. Modernist
4. Fundamentalist

Secularists are basically the people who like liberalism and western policies. They do not consider religion anyway. Traditionalists are the people who do not adopt any invasions and stuck with their own traditions. Fundamentalists reject modernism and modern culture and want to impose their own doctrine of Islam. Taliban, Al-Qaeda and other militant groups are come under this umbrella called fundamentalists. On the other hand modernists want to survive with modern world. They want the religion with the modern trends. Freedom of thoughts, liberty, Social personal stability and equality are the basic elements of this category. These two categories are the groups in the Islamic states that clashes often with their ideologies. Modernists do not accept fundamentalists' policies and this happened same with fundamentalist groups.

Review of Tehrik-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP)

Giustozzi (2009) says that TTP is the militant organization under several other groups. TTP is neither Al-Qaeda nor Afghan Taliban. Rather they have their separate identity and recognized as the militant group under the leadership of Baitullah Mahsod. They have the ir own philosophy and ideology. Their main plan to resist against the Pakistan Government, impose the law of sharia and they are unite with the afghan Taliban. Ilahi (2010) says that Tehrek-e-Taliban Pakistan is a growing threat for Pakistan and international community. The TTP and Al-Qaeda is operating on the Pakistani tribal areas. They emerged in Pakistan when the number of Al-Qaeda

and Afghan Taliban fled towards Pakistan at the result of the operation by the American forces in 2001 in Afghanistan. In 2001 some tribesmen supported the Afghan Taliban and organized the TTP. From that time they are operating in Pakistan. TTP is considering as the biggest threat for the Pakistan and for the whole world as well. They have policy to withdraw US forces from Afghanistan, impose sharia law and the threaten Pakistan as they want made them. TTP are very small in number, away from the basic facilities and technologies living in the remote areas. Question is that with such a low living standard of these Taliban why the government and the American forces could not finish them? Pande (2011) says that the development of TTP is lie down at 2001 American attack on Afghanistan when afghan Taliban and Al-Qaeda were escaped towards Pakistan. This organization further nurtures here and develops its own policy. Pakistan wanted to keep sustain in their relations with these militants because in previous they had long term relations with them. Their foreign policy was not negating these groups previously and the former president was even felt reluctant to turn over his policy towards them because Pakistan have weak end at Indian border and they considered them to helping factor for them. Fair et all (2010) in their report says that there were number of cease fire between Pakistan go vernment and the TTP but all in vain. Baituallah Mahsood and his command are to be considered culpable for the attacks in Pakistan from 2006 to onward. If the authorities will not take action towards them they will be sustained and more developed further and may be caused for any bigger attack more horrible from their previous attacks. Cohen (2011) says that TTP is against the Pakistan government because they think Pakistan as the sub servant of America. Siddiqa (2011) says that there is much difference between afghan Taliban and Pakistan Taliban. TTP has no central command. They are against the Pakistan policy whereas the afghan Taliban are not interested in attacks in Pakistan. They have their own political interests in Afghanistan.

Review of Afghan Taliban

Hussein (2003) says that Afghan Taliban have nothing about Islam. They just think about their self, having radical image of Islam. They even do not know the enlighten features of Islam in which the social and cultural patterns are existing. They have their own tone about religion and want to impose that destructed image over everyone in Afghanistan. Their extremist policy is not only in the interest of themselves but in the interest of entire region as well. Pande (2011) says that the problem with afghan Taliban started when they sheltered Usama Bin Ladin (an international Jihad Group). They were in the problem that time collected resources from Afghanistan and Pakistan and build strong ties with them. Afghan Taliban were denied to transfer the detention of Usama to the US and this was led the War in Afghanistan and build a new government under the leadership of Hamid Kerzai. Rothstein & Arqulla (2012) says that TTP is against with Pakistan for joining War on terrorism with America and they threat and terrified the Pakistan government with their terrorist attacks for pressurizing the Pakistan government to not support this war. Even their actions in Pakistan create tensions in their relations with other groups like wise Haqqani group and Quetta Shura.

Marsdon (1998) says that Afghan Taliban main concern towards Afghanistan territory was to eradicate corruption and maintain Law and order. Maintain their government in Afghanistan is their second objective even they didn't not have previously experience for this. Lansford et all (2009) says that Afghan Taliban get vast support from the afghan people initially when they made them free from the fifteen years of civil war. They get lots of support until they were majority in Pushtons and received support from ethnic Tajik Rabani. After capturing Kabul

in 1996 they were in favored by all; but after that their imposition of strict sheriya law. In 1998 they fall the Mazar e Sharif and till then they captured 90% of the country and till then they had only one enemy and that was the united front of north alliance. In 1992 afghan Taliban provided support to Usama Bin laden in Sudan operations. Because of the pressure of United State and Saudi Arabia, Sudan expelled Usama Bin laden from Sudan in 1996. This was the time when Afghan Captured power and they sheltered Usama Bin Laden. After that Afghanistan was the place where different terrorist organizations emerged from Chechnya, Lebnan, Kashmir, Palestine and Pakistan as well. When America demanding surrenders for laden they negate to transfer and after that Afghanistan was under the crises and same as to Pakistan as well. Combs (2003) says that the Afghan war causes the fled of Al-Qaeda and afghan Taliban to Pakistan are again going back to Afghanistan and strengthen their power again to recapture the Afghan Territory for the sake of establish their own laws.

Theoretical frame work

The theoretical framework goes to the framing theory of Robert Entman which plainly states that the framing process is the process which selects some piece of reality and makes that realty more silent and real by discussing again and again. Frames have lots of power to drag our attention in a particular way. We think and perceive the world, by noticing something more than other things; this is what frames do to us. Frames guide us by including some elements and excluding as well. Entman (1993). The people in real world have not detectable approach while they are processing it. Instead of finding reality they much rely on the things that they have an easy access to them. It is suggested that finding frames in communication process is a normal thing. They are included in communicator, text, receiver, sender and the culture at large. Frames influence and suggest the definition, troubles, diagnoses, moral judgments and suggest remedies. Frames suggest a suitable notion in which we see the things otherwise the patterns remain unnoticed and neutral. Frames mould the information in a suitable way in which we perceive these information.

Entman says

“Frames reside in the specific properties of the news narratives that encourage those perceiving and thinking about events to develop particular understandings of them”

Frames can be detected in the words, phrases, pictures, metaphors and the things like that. In war on terror frame, different nations perceive different frames out of it. In this case cultural approach is to be worked out. The important issues, like war on terror, the communication suggestions are filled by the years. These frames worked by the stimulating effect on people by the policy makers and the communicators on the people. Rees (2010)

Importance of the Study

This research work is an attempt to study the portrayal of militants in Pakistan and American press. Pakistan is the country who is suffering a lot because of militancy. America is the country who started war on terror after 9/11 against militants. The both countries are the key partners in the war on terror. On the whole it is important to know their press behaviors towards militants and militancy that makes study significant. The main areas on which the research having focus are

1. To analyze the treatment on militants and militancy in Daily Dawn and Daily New York Times
2. To find out the similarities in the daily New York Times and daily Dawn regarding militants and militancy
3. To analyze the differences in daily Dawn and Daily New York Times regarding militants and militancy

Research Questions

1. What is the treatment of daily Dawn and daily New York Times towards Al-Qaida, TTP and AT?
2. What are the similarities of daily Dawn and daily New York Times towards militants?
3. What are the differences of daily Dawn and daily New York Times towards militants?

Hypothesis

H₀

It is more likely that Daily Dawn is more negative towards militants

H₁

It is more likely that New York Times is more negative towards militants.

Rationale

1. It is more likely that Dawn being a Pakistani newspaper will more negative towards militants as Pakistan is suffering a lot from militants and militancy
2. It is more likely that daily New York Times being an American newspaper will more negative towards militants as America is the country who started war against militants.

Research methodology

This research work is fundamentally the portrayal of militants. The qualitative and quantitative content analysis of New York Times and daily Dawn was being done to observe the treatment of newspapers towards militants. To observe the press policy, the treatment of editorials of both newspapers was experiential. The time period of ten years was chosen by the researcher.

Operationalization

The militants further break up in three categories. These categories are

- Al-Qaida
- Tahrek-e-Taliban
- Afghan Taliban

Data presentation

The American and Pakistan press completely consider the militants as enemy. American press gives heavy coverage to Al-Qaida while Pakistan press gave weighty treatment to the Tehrek-e-Taliban Pakistan. Overall both Pakistan and American press give negative treatment to the militants.

Portrayal of militants by Daily Dawn and New York Times

This table shows the overall portrayal of militants in daily Dawn and daily New York Times. Daily Dawn gave Al-Qaida to 21.8%, TTP to 49.5% and AT to 28.7% editorials, while New York Times gave 53.2% to Al-Qaida, 9% to TTP and 38% to AT editorials. Daily dawn gave high coverage to the TTP and to some extent equal coverage to AT and Al-Qaida whereas Daily NYT gave noticeable coverage of 53.2% to Al-Qaida, AT to 38% and TTP to very less coverage of 9% editorial.

Table: 1 Portrayal of Militants

	Al-Qaida	TTP	AT
Daily Dawn	21.8%	49.5%	28.7%
Daily NYT	53.2%	9%	38%

Slants in Daily Dawn

Table 2 depicts that daily dawn gave equal 0% positive coverage to all Al-Qaida, TTP and AT. Dawn is 21.8% negative towards Al-Qaida, 49.5% negative to TTP and 19.5% negative converge to the AT. Dawn gave no neutral coverage of editorials towards Al-Qaida and TTP, this shows the clear stance of Dawn towards Al-Qaeda and TTP which is Negative whereas 9.2% Neutral treatment of editorials was found by researcher towards AT.

Table: 2 Slants of militants in Daily Dawn

	Positive	Negative	Neutral
Al-Qaida	0%	21.8%	0%
TTP	0%	49.5%	0%
AT	0%	19.5	9.2%

Slants in Daily NYT

Like Daily Dawn, Daily NYT gave no positive coverage to the militants. It gave Al-Qaeda to 53.2%, TTP to 4% and AT to 35% negative coverage, while no neutral editorials were found towards Al-Qaeda. It remains 5.1% neutral towards TTP and 2.7% negative towards AT.

Table: 3 Slants of militants in Daily NYT

	Positive	Negative	Neutral
Al-Qaida	0%	53.2%	0%
TTP	0%	4%	5.1%
AT	0%	35%	2.7%

Overall Slants of the militants in Daily Dawn and Daily NYT

figure 1 shows the overall slanting of the militants in daily Dawn and Daily NYT. Both NYT and Dawn gave no positive stance towards militants. Dawn gave 90.8% negative stance whereas NYT remain Negative with 92.2%. it shows that both newspaper remain negative towards militants with very less difference

Figure:1

Framing of Militants In Daily Dawn And Daily NYT Figure 2 & 3

Figure 2 and 3 shows the framing of the militants. There are two frames which are Militants as innocent and militants as enemy. Both newspapers have equally treated the militants as enemy with 100% treatment. The researcher did not find not even a single frame of militants as innocent.

Conclusion

The research depicts that militants are considered enemy in both Pakistan and American press and gave negative stance to it. America's main focus is on Al-Qaida as the Al-Qaida was the major cause of destruction of 9/11 and Pakistan press's main focus is on the TTP because this is the TTP which is caused number of casualties in Pakistan. Apart from that overall impression of both press negative to militants but New York Time is little more negative towards militants as compare to daily Dawn so our alternative hypothesis is proved right that It is more likely that New York Times is more negative towards militants. Militancy is the biggest fear around the globe. As per our literature review, America gave boost to the militants in Pakistan to gain some interests overall. But after getting the interest, they left those elements of destruction alone. The need was to utilize those factors in some productive way but the situation was not like that. This is the time when those all factors converted towards revenge and because of the destructing policies from both Pakistan and America it got boost again. The behavior of militants towards innocent people is too much worse and it should be condemned. Thousand of people met with undue death only because of their wild activities. The time is to understand their mindsets and solve the problems accordingly. Power never ends with power. This is the responsibility of the governments, press and the policy makers of both countries to make some policies which paying attention on solutions rather destruction.

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